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LINEAR AND NONLINEAR RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN INTERNATIONAL RESERVES AND ECONOMIC GROWTH: EVIDENCE FROM ALGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Algeria's international reserves have grown rapidly since 2000, reflecting rising prices for exported oil. International reserves management represents a crucial aspect of macroeconomic policy to help achieve overall economic growth. The study investigates linear and nonlinear causality between international reserves and economic growth. Earlier studies have ignored the nonlinear behaviour which could be caused by structural breaks. In this study both linear and nonlinear causality tests are applied to examine causal relationship between the two for Algeria. It is found that there is bidirectional causality between international reserves and economic growth with respect to the linear causality but a unidirectional causality exists running from economic growth to international reserves with respect to nonlinear causality. On the basis of these results, we suggest that the policy formulators of Algerian government to promote and recover oil and gas sector to achieve the goal of economic growth.

Keywords- Algeria, economic growth, international reserves, Nonlinearity test.

1. Introduction

International reserves are 'those external assets that are readily available to and controlled by monetary authorities for direct financing of payment imbalances through intervention in exchange markets to affect the currency exchange rate, and/or for other purposes' (Balance of Payments Manual, [International Monetary Fund], 2014). International reserves or foreign exchange reserves are a country's external assets that include Gold, Special Drawing Rights (SDRs), foreign currency deposits and Bonds held by monetary authorities, Gold and Reserve position at the IMF.

Algeria's foreign currency reserves have grown rapidly since 2000, reflecting rising prices for exported oil. At the end of 2014, international reserves totalled US\$179.62 billion, up from US\$12 billion in 2000 and the equivalent of almost three years of imports. In 2010 the estimated inflation rate was 3.9 percent. In 2010, the IMF voiced concerns about poor management of Algeria's monetary system and inflation. In April 2014, a report focusing on world economic projections was published by the IMF, according to which it was predicted that, in 2015, Algeria's economic growth would fall by 1.5%, while unemployment would rise by 1.2%. This was what the reason we chose Algeria for our analysis.

Table 1
International Reserves Holdings in Algeria (Weeks of imports)

Year	US Dollar in billion
2000	44
2005	96
2010	148
2014	112

Source: World Development Indicators/authors' calculation.

International reserves cannot be accumulated by monetary authorities indefinitely. Too much reserve hoarding requires significant sterilization costs, as negative spread between interest received on reserves and interest paid on nation's public debt rises with reserve accumulation. Moreover, persistent reserve accumulation will generate inflationary pressures if capital flows are not sterilized, enhancing the possibility of domestic financial crises. On the contrary, if these monetary authorities determine to stop accumulating US dollar reserves, they could trigger an unexpected depreciation of the US dollar and a sharp increase in interest rates. Given the possible impact on world interest rates, growth, and financial stability, the issue of international reserves accumulation is of substantial importance.

International reserves management represents a crucial aspect of macroeconomic policy in the era of high capital mobility and cross-border transactions. Augmented financial integration generally makes a country vulnerable to financial crisis due to sudden reversals in capital flows. Therefore, holding a huge stockpile of international reserves can be an effective policy for developing economies given their restricted access to international capital markets. (Aizenman & Marion 2002).

Table 2
International Reserves Holdings in Algeria

Year	US Dollar in billion
2000	12.02
2005	56.30
2010	162.61
2014	179.62

Source: World Development Indicators/authors' calculation.

2. Objectives of the study

The objective of the study is based on the question whether economic growth stays responsible for large accumulation of international reserves and vice versa? How does economic growth linked with the foreign exchange reserves show a nonlinear behaviour? This study tries to answer these questions by re-examining the linear causality between international reserves and economic growth using Granger causality technique suggested by Granger C. (1988). The study also investigates the non-linear relationship between the two, which is new to available literature.

3. Review of Literature

Heller (1966) evaluated the optimum stock of international reserves and followed rational optimizing decision to equate marginal cost and benefit of keeping international reserves.

Actual reserves were compared with the results obtained for every economy in the sample to assess international reserves adequacy.

Frenkel and Jovanovic (1981) revised Heller's model to determine optimum level of international reserves. They employed time series data for 22 economies and concluded that their estimations were nearer to the theoretical forecastings. They found that almost all empirical studies considered real variables to determine the demand for foreign exchange reserves. These variables include: export, import, external debt- both short-term and long-term and trade shocks

Yii Siing Wong , Chong Mun Ho & Brian Dollery (2012) the purpose of this article is to examine both linear and nonlinear relationships between exchange rate volatility and import flows for the US and Malaysia. The linear relationship will be tested by using the bound test approach proposed by Pesaran et al. (2001), while the nonlinear relationship is tested using nonlinear causality proposed by Hiemstra and Jones (1994). This article has examined both linear and nonlinear relationships for Malaysia and the US using data for the periods 1975/2009 and 1980/2009, respectively. The empirical results show no cointegration exists between exchange rate volatility and imports for both Malaysia and the US. We can therefore conclude that a stable exchange rate system would promote imports. The relationship between exchange rate volatility and import flows is in nonlinear form. This indicates that a change in exchange rate volatility would have a greater effect on import flows, either increasing or decreasing the import volume compared to the linear relationship

Shiok Ye Lim and Chong Mun Ho (2013) investigated the relationship between export and economic growth for Asean-5 countries for the period of 1953-2008. They utilized both linear and nonlinear methodology. They employed Augmented dickey fuller and Breitung's nonparametric unit root test, Johansen cointegration test, Hiemstra and Jones nonlinearity test, Diks and Panchenko nonparametric test and BDS test. A standard linear vector autoregressive model was used by them to trace the direction of causality of export growth and economic growth. Their study uncovered linear and nonlinear relationship between export growth and economic growth in case of Malaysia, Thailand, Indonesia and Singapore while no relationship linear or nonlinear was found in case of Philippines.

4. Data description and Research Methodology

4.1 Data source:

In this study the variables used were the ratio of international reserves excluding gold to GDP (IR) and economic growth (ECON) proxied by real GDP. Time series data were employed. The study used quarterly data from 1985q1 to 2014q4 extracted from IMF's International Financial Statistics and World Development Indicators of the World Bank. Obviously, the data for these variables might be affected seasonally; hence, in order to retard the seasonal factors, we used the X11 adjustment programme proposed by the U.S. Bureau of the Census 1965. Table 3 represents the vital descriptive statistics of each variable. The average IR is 51.66429 billion US dollars with a standard deviation of 69.21488, a maximum international reserves of 195.0520 billion US dollars and a minimum of 0.469707 billion US dollars. The average ECON is 22.97408 billion US dollars with a standard deviation of 14.35088, a maximum economic growth of 53.75181 billion US dollars and a minimum of 10.24481 billion US dollars.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics

	IR	ECON
Mean	51.66429	22.97408
Median	8.188460	15.20519
Maximum	195.0520	53.75181
Minimum	0.469707	10.24481
Std. Dev.	69.21488	14.35088
Observations	120	120

Note: ECON and IR represents economic growth and international reserves respectively.

4.2 Linear Ganger causality test:

The bivariate Granger causality tests help in examining the relationship between two variables. The two variables X and Y evaluate whether the past values of X are useful to predict Y, and Y is said to be Granger-caused by X if X helps to predict Y, and vice versa. On the basis of Granger's causality test, we used the vector autoregression (VAR) model proposed by Sims (1980) to perform the causality tests. Let a bivariate VAR model be

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha_1 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{1i} \Delta X_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_{1j} \Delta Y_{t-j} + v_{1t} \quad \dots(1)$$

$$\Delta X_t = \alpha_2 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_{2i} \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{j=1}^n \gamma_{2j} \Delta X_{t-j} + v_{2t} \quad \dots(2)$$

4.3 The Hiemstra and Jones (1994) Nonlinearity Test

Applying the linear approach (such as the Granger causality test) leads to a problem, namely, a low power in detecting a nonlinear causal relation (**Baek & Brock, 1992; Hiemstra & Jones, 1994**). Hiemstra and Jones (1994) revised a version of the Baek and Brock (1992) test, which is different from Granger's (1969) linear causality test. They suggested a non-linear Granger's causality test based on non-parametric estimators of progressive relationship within and across time series. Let $F(X_t|L_{t-1})$ represent the restricted probability distribution of X_t given the information set L_{t-1} , which comprises an L_x -length lagged vector of X_t and an L_y -length lagged vector of Y_t . If the vector of past Y-values is eliminated from the information set in such a way that the distribution of current X-values is not affected, Y is supposed to not Granger-cause X. Hence, the null hypothesis of Hiemstra and Jones is expressed as follows:

$$H_0: F(X_t|L_{t-1}) = F(X_t|L_{t-1} - Y_{t-1}^{ly}) \quad \dots(3)$$

Here, Y_{t-1}^{ly} represents the $t - l_y -$ length lagged vector of Y and

$$Y_{t-1}^{ly} = (Y_{t-1}^{ly}, Y_{t-1}^{ly+1}, \dots, Y_{t-1})$$

The null hypothesis given in equation (1) implies that for all $\epsilon > 0$

$$P(\|X_t^n - X_s^n\| < \epsilon \mid \|X_{t-1x}^{1x} - X_{s-1x}^{1x}\| < \epsilon, \|Y_{t-1y}^{1y} - Y_{s-1y}^{1y}\| < \epsilon) = P(\|X_t^n - X_s^n\| < \epsilon \mid \|X_{t-1x}^{1x} - X_{s-1x}^{1x}\| < \epsilon) \dots(4)$$

Here, P(A|B) denotes the conditional probability of A provided B and $\|\dots\|$ represents supreme norm. Equation (2) asserts that in addition to lagged Ly-length lagged vector of Y_t being ϵ -closed, the conditional probability that two arbitrary n-length lead vectors of X_t are within distance ϵ , given that the lagged L_x -length lagged vector of X_t is ϵ -closed, will be the same. Moreover, Hiemstra and Jones show that T-statistics follow normal distribution under Eq. (1):

$$T_{statistics} = \sqrt{q} \left[\frac{C_1(n + L_x, L_y, \epsilon)}{C_2(L_x, L_y, \epsilon)} - \frac{C_3(n + L_x, \epsilon)}{C_4(L_x, \epsilon)} \right] \sim Q(0, \sigma^2, n, L_x, L_y, \epsilon) \dots(5)$$

Here, $C_1(n + L_x, L_y, \epsilon) = P(\|X_{t-1x}^{n+1x} - X_{s-1x}^{n+1x}\| < \epsilon, \|Y_{t-1y}^{1y} - Y_{s-1y}^{1y}\| < \epsilon)$,

$$C_2(L_x, L_y, \epsilon) = P(\|X_{t-1x}^{1x} - X_{s-1x}^{1x}\| < \epsilon, \|Y_{t-1y}^{1y} - Y_{s-1y}^{1y}\| < \epsilon),$$

$$C_3(n + L_x, \epsilon) = P(\|X_{t-1x}^{n+1x} - X_{s-1x}^{n+1x}\| < \epsilon),$$

$$C_4(L_x, \epsilon) = P(\|X_{t-1x}^{1x} - X_{s-1x}^{1x}\| < \epsilon).$$

5. Empirical Analysis and Findings

5.1 Unit root tests results:

Before conducting the Granger causality test, we applied the Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillips-Perron unit root tests to check the stationarity all variables. The results are reported in Table 4. This table denotes that under the 5 per cent significance level, the ADF t-statistics of the level term in IR and ECON were -1.49 and 1.40 respectively; this showed that the null hypothesis of the series with a unit root cannot be rejected. Moreover, after first difference, the t-statistics of IR and ECON were -1.82 and -3.05 respectively. The same results were found when Phillips-Perron unit root test was applied. The PP t-statistics in level term for IR and ECON were 1.06 and 1.41; after the first difference, the statistics of IR and ECON were -3.32 and -5.75. It was found that under the 5 per cent significance level, the null hypothesis of unit root can be rejected. This showed that variables were found stationary only after first difference. Hence, linear Granger causality test was applied to the two first-differenced variables.

Table 4: Unit root tests results

Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF)			Phillips-Perron (PP)	
Variables	Level	1 st difference	Level	1 st difference
IR	-1.49 (2)	-1.82** (2)	1.06 (5)	-3.32** (4)
ECON	1.40 (4)	-3.05** (5)	1.41 (3)	-5.75*(3)

Note: The numbers in parenthesis are the selected lag orders based on AIC criteria. * and ** denotes rejection of null hypothesis at 1 per cent and 5 per cent significance level respectively.

5.2 Granger causality test results

The linear causality test results of IR and ECON were listed in Table 5. The lag selection was based on Akaike information Criteria (AIC) which showed the optimum lag as 8. There are two Granger null hypotheses that should be focused on: testing whether the IR will Granger-cause ECON, and testing whether ECON will Granger-cause IR. It was found that under the 5 per cent significance level, the null hypothesis yielded Wald test values of 15.70 for ECON; this showed that the IR will Granger-cause ECON. On the other hand, under the 5 per cent significance level the null hypothesis yielded Wald test values of 19.30, for ECON; this showed that ECON will Granger-cause IR. These two results prove that there is a bidirectional causality between international reserves and economic growth in case of Algeria.

Table 5: Linear causality test results

Variable	Direction	Chi-sq value
ECON	IR \Rightarrow ECON	15.70 (0.04)**
	ECON \Rightarrow IR	19.30 (0.01)*

Note: Figures in parenthesis are p values; * and ** denotes 1 per cent and 5 per cent significance level respectively.

Clearly, the results presented above are not steady with the economic intuition. The study speculated that the reason for this estimate bias might be due to the nonlinear causality. If so, then, instead of the linear Granger causality test, the nonlinear Granger causality test would appear to be more appropriate. To test for nonlinearity, the BDS test proposed by Brock et al. (1987) was performed on the residual series of VAR models to test the i.i.d. assumption. The BDS test suggested by Brock et al. (1987) would be helpful in proving the speculation of estimation bias may be due to the nonlinear causality by using the i.i.d. test to determine whether the residual in the linear model is nonlinear or not. If the assumption of i.i.d. is rejected, a nonlinear relation will emerge among the variables, sustaining the speculation. We conducted this test; the results of which are explained below.

Table 6: BDS test results

Standard deviation	Dimension	ECON
0.5	2	5.05 (0.00)*
0.5	3	8.10 (0.00)*
0.5	4	11.17 (0.00)*

Note: Figures in parenthesis are bootstrap p values; * denotes 1% significance level.

5.3 Nonlinear causality test results:

The result of the BDS test are listed in Table 6. The study found that under the 5 per cent significance level, irrespective of the dimension, the null of the i.i.d residual was rejected in the linear model of ECON and IR. On the basis of these results, and by comparing them with those obtained in Table 7, we further analyzed the nonlinear causality test proposed by Hiemstra and Jones (1994) to test the causality relation between these two variables. Under the lag orders of 4, 5, 6 and 7, the study concluded that there was a unidirectional causality between economic growth and international reserves. Clearly, these empirical results are consistent with the economic intuition.

Table 7: Nonlinear causality test results

$L_x = L_y$	$H_0: IR \not\Rightarrow Econ$		$L_x = L_y$	$H_0: Econ \not\Rightarrow IR$	
	CS	TS		CS	TS
4	-0.333	-3.446	4	0.126	1.301*
5	-0.367	-3.793	6	0.298	3.084*
6	-0.354	-3.659	7	0.312	3.226*
7	-0.321	-3.316	8	0.381	3.939*

Note: $L_x = L_y$ represents the numbers of lag orders by the nonlinear causality test. Periods 4-7 are selected from quarterly data. CS and TS, denote the difference between the two conditional probabilities and the standardized test statistics respectively. * represents 1% significance level with critical value of 0.582.

6. Conclusion

In contrast to previous studies, this study investigated the nonlinear and linear causality between international reserves (IR) and economic growth (ECON). The study applied the Augmented Dickey Fuller and Phillips-Perron unit root tests to check the stationarity issue of the variables. All variables were found stationary after the first difference. Therefore, linear Granger causality test was applied to the variables. The linear causality test results indicated that there is a bidirectional causality between IR and ECON in Algeria. The study suspected that this bidirectional relationship may be due to estimation bias or structural breaks caused by some significant economic event such as financial crises. Furthermore, The study used the nonlinear causality test suggested by Hiemstra and Jones (1994) to test the possibility of nonlinear causality among variables. The empirical results revealed that there was a unidirectional causality between IR and ECON.

On the basis of the empirical results, we are inclined to put forth two perspectives. First, facing continuously fluctuation in oil prices and coping with the international economic pressure, Algeria should actively seek other international reserves related strategies such as investing these into long term capital projects to sustain economic growth. Second, the principal exports of Algeria are petroleum, natural gas, and petroleum products. Algeria has enormous possibilities to boost its economic growth, including huge foreign-exchange reserves derived from oil and gas. The spike in oil prices and the government's tight fiscal policy, as well as a large increase in the trade surplus and the near tripling of foreign exchange reserves may help the country's finances. A development strategy targeting stronger, sustained growth would create more jobs, especially for young people, and alleviate the housing shortage the country is facing. Another strategic option is to revitalise the process intended to diversify the economy starting with the non-oil sector while deepening the reforms needed for the structural transformation of the economy.

Due to the topical importance of the relationship between international reserves and economic growth and the lack of uniformity in empirical findings, however, we caution that government of Algeria need to be extra careful in implementing relevant policies and the policies should be based on sound economic analyses. In this regard, our study represents one step closer to economic truth, but further studies utilizing newer samples and newer methodologies are clearly warranted.

7. Limitations of the study

- ❖ The study is confined to one economy only. Further research may be carried out considering more economies altogether.

- ❖ The study is performed under bivariate framework. Further studies may be done considering multivariate framework.

8. References

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